

THE LEAKY PIPELINE PHENOMENON: WOMEN MINORITY RESEARCHERS (WMR) IN ACADEMIA

• The leaky pipeline

Minority and women researchers face barriers in advancing through academic ranks, limiting recognition, support, and opportunities compared to their non-minority (male or white) counterparts.

• Diversity, equity and inclusion

Distinct but interconnected concepts. Institutions mostly focus on (disciplinary) **diversity**, but this alone doesn't guarantee equity and inclusion. **Equity** requires addressing power imbalances and systemic disadvantages, often through providing additional support and opportunities for the disadvantaged. **Inclusion** ensures that the voices of diverse individuals are heard.

• Why focusing on WMRs?

WMRs are often excluded from initiatives that focus solely on gender or race, so we focus on this group to ensure no one is left behind.

Intersectionality: examines how overlapping marginalized identities create unique experiences of bias. WMRs face both sexism and racism, amplifying challenges in academia—the "Double Bind" theory.

GLOSSARY

- **Glass ceiling & sticky floor** describe barriers faced by women and minorities at different stages. The glass ceiling blocks access to top positions due to hidden criteria and exclusion from male-dominated networks (social capital). The sticky floor keeps them in lower-status, insecure roles with limited mobility.
- **Old boy network:** network of male researchers who support each other through informal channels, and that often excludes women due to both gender identity and norms.
- **Tokenism:** Women who advance may become "token" figures, discouraging others from following. They often adopt survival strategies—speaking out (risking penalties), accepting sexism, or blending in by adopting "male" traits.
- **Cultural taxation:** unacknowledged emotional and service labor performed by women in universities.
- **Epistemic exclusion:** the devaluation of scholarship, where researchers feel their work is overlooked or undervalued. The *Matilda Effect* is a specific form of epistemic exclusion, where women's contributions are often overlooked or credited to male colleagues.

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WHAT LEADS TO THIS LEAKY PIPELINE PHENOMENON?

1

• Lack of clear and transparent promotion criteria

WMRs struggle to access institutional agendas, unwritten rules of promotion, and crucial networks, excluding them from influential decision-making spheres.

Transparent, unambiguous and well-communicated promotion criteria

2

• Disproportionally high workloads of invisible service work

WMRs face higher standards, heavier teaching loads, and more undervalued and underrewarded service work. This 'cultural taxation' limits research time and leads to backlash when they decline excessive demands.

- *Equal distribution of labor in departments (e.g. with dashboards or audits)*
- *Rewarding service alone can overburden WMRs and reduce research time.*
- *Protect those who speak up against retaliation.*

3

• Sexism and racial discrimination

WMRs frequently experience gendered microaggressions, challenged authority, and assumptions of inferiority. They face more student disrespect and poor evaluations, contributing to anxiety, stress, burnout, and lower productivity.

- *Acknowledge the importance of identity in knowledge production over 'objectivity.'*
- *Promote inclusivity, diversity, and equity through policies and trainings.*
- *Develop metrics to monitor and share the institution's diversity efforts.*
- *Provide WMRs with role models to counter inferiority beliefs due to racist and sexist experiences.*

4

• Exclusion from professional and support networks

WMRs are often less integrated into academic culture, making collaboration, networking, and departmental navigation harder. Exclusion from 'old boys' networks limits access to knowledge regarding research resources and funding, reinforcing the sticky floor effect.

Promote culturally competent mentorship, where mentors educate themselves on gender and race and help WMRs build networks and navigate departmental politics.

5

• Precarious working conditions

Short term job contracts and the need for mobility in research particularly negatively influence WMRs who are engaged in caretaking obligations.

- *Provide strong support for parents/caretakers and offer flexible work options.*
- *In evaluations, do not expect uniform productivity—allow tenure clock pauses for childbirth, adoption, or caregiving of family members, including for men to promote gender equity.*
- *Establish committees to assess equity in policies.*

6

• Lack of (financial) support for engaging in true research interests

WMRs are often assigned tasks they're less interested in or research that aligns less with their values, negatively impacting their productivity and evaluation.

- *Provide possibility for WMRs to grow in their careers.*
- *Reward research on diversity, equity and inclusion*
- *Develop targeted research and academic support programs for WMRs.*
- *Value nonconventional research topics that incorporate cultural or community needs of WMRs.*

suggested solutions